

MEAN FIELD HOMOGENIZATION OF DISCONTINUOUS FIBER REINFORCED POLYMERS AND PARAMETER IDENTIFICATION OF BIAXIAL TENSILE TESTS THROUGH INVERSE MODELING

Malte Schemmann¹, Barthel Brylka², Viktor Müller³, Maria L. Kehrner⁴ and Thomas Böhlke⁵
Institute of Engineering Mechanics (ITM), Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)

Kaiserstr. 12, Building 10.23, 76131 Karlsruhe, Germany

<http://www.itm.kit.edu/cm>

¹Email: malte.schemmann@kit.edu

²Email: bartholomaeus.brylka@kit.edu

³Email: viktor.mueller@kit.edu

⁴Email: maria.kehrner@kit.edu

⁵Email: thomas.boehlke@kit.edu

Keywords: *fiber reinforced composites, biaxial tensile testing, inverse parameter identification, homogenization, interaction direct derivative estimate*

ABSTRACT

The present article deals with the characterization of the mechanical properties of long fiber reinforced thermoplastics (LFT), the resulting inverse parameter identification and homogenization based on fiber orientation distribution. To gain a better insight into this inhomogeneous and anisotropic material behavior, biaxial tensile tests on cruciform specimen are performed. The full 3D strain field is measured via digital image correlation (DIC). The observed results including inelastic effects are discussed in detail for uniaxial and biaxial loading paths. The anisotropic material properties are identified through inverse modeling by comparison of the heterogeneous experimental and simulated strain fields. A Gauss-Newton type algorithm is used to identify the optimal parameter set [12]. Hereby the polymer composite is assumed to behave as a viscoelastic Maxwell material, to take rate-dependent effects into account. The identified linear elastic material parameters are compared to homogenized properties based on fiber orientation distributions obtained by micro-computed tomography. Meanfield approaches such as the interaction direct derivative estimate [20] and a Mori-Tanaka scheme are used to determine the macroscopic material properties.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to their high lightweight potential, economical mass-production and excellent formability, LFT is increasingly used for nonstructural components in the automotive sector [1]. The application of this class of materials is however hindered by a lack of an understanding for robust modeling the whole process chain as well as the process related thermo-mechanical properties. The material class under consideration is LFT-D (long fiber reinforced thermoplastics manufactured in a direct in-line process). The orientation and length distribution of the fibers in this material is highly heterogeneous and anisotropic. As a result the material behavior is spatially heterogeneous and anisotropic in a process sensitive way.

Schnur and Zabaras [18] introduced an optimization procedure for inverse parameter identification with the Finite Element Method (FEM). A correlation function is introduced to describe the deviation of the experimental and simulated data.

In the past many approaches were suggested to optimize the correlation function. Gradient free procedures such as a neural network computation [4] and evolutionary algorithms [16] need no additional model information but require a comparably high computational effort.

An overview of different gradient methods for inverse parameter identification is given by Ponthot and

Kleinermann [17]. The required gradient can either be estimated by a finite difference scheme [18, 6] or calculated analytically [14, 13].

The development of full field measurement techniques allowed for a parameter identification of inhomogeneous strain and displacement fields. Lecompte et. al. [12] identified the anisotropic elastic behavior of glass fiber reinforced epoxy.

A direct tensor notation is preferred throughout the text. Tensor components are expressed by latin indices and Einstein's summation convention is applied. The composition of two second-order or two fourth-order tensors is formulated by \mathbf{AB} and $\mathbf{A}\mathbf{B}$. A linear mapping of second-order tensors by a fourth-order tensor is written as $\mathbf{A} = \mathbb{C}[\mathbf{B}]$. The scalar product is denoted by $\mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{B}$. We define the composition operator \square via $(\mathbf{A} \square \mathbf{B})[\mathbf{C}] = \mathbf{ACB}$, the dyadic product operator \otimes as $(\mathbf{A} \otimes \mathbf{B})[\mathbf{C}] = (\mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{C}) \mathbf{A}$, and the contraction operator $\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket$ with $(\mathbf{a} \otimes \mathbf{b}) \cdot (\mathbb{C}[\mathbf{a} \otimes \mathbf{b}]) = (\mathbf{a} \otimes \mathbf{a}) \cdot (\mathbb{C}[\mathbf{b} \otimes \mathbf{b}])$. Arbitrary vectors \mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b} , second-order tensors \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{C} and the fourth-order tensor \mathbb{C} are used in the foregoing definitions. The identity on symmetric second-order tensors is denoted by \mathbb{I}^s . Completely symmetric and traceless, i.e. irreducible tensors are denoted with a prime, e.g., \mathbf{A}' .

2 LONG FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPSTICS MANUFACTURED IN A DIRECT LINE PROCESS

The long glass fiber reinforced polypropylene is manufactured in a direct line (LFT-D) in an in-line compounding (ILC) system. For an understanding of the material, especially its inhomogeneity and anisotropy, the process is introduced in the following.

Figure 1 shows a schematic overview of the production line. The polypropylene matrix and additives

Fig. 1: LFT-D ILC manufacturing process (Source: Fraunhofer ICT [7])

are compounded in a twin screw extruder and exit through a film die, where the compound enters the twin screw device with the fiber rovings. The continuous fibers are cut and distributed by the screws. The servo die doses the plastificate onto the conveyor belt, before it is cut and placed into the mold for compression molding. Due to the separated heating of the polymer matrix this gentle fiber processing leads to a compared to a, compared to LFT-Pellets long, fiber lengths of 20 – 40 mm [11].

The rectangular mold dimensions are 250 mm × 800 mm × 4 mm, whereas the plastificate is placed on one side of the mold. As the mold closes in the compression molding process, the compound fills the mold by flowing in the x_1 -direction (see Figure 2). Jeffrey's equation expresses how shear flow leads to an increased degree of fiber orientation along the flow direction, in this case the x_1 -direction.

Fig. 2: Manufactured LFT plate with cruciform specimens

Three cruciform specimen were cut out of the LFT plate by water jet cutting. Figure 2 shows their positions as well as the markers used for integrated strain measurement by the Video XTens. On the other side of the specimen, a gray value pattern is applied for DIC.

3 BIAXIAL TENSILE EXPERIMENTS

The specimens are tested in an electro-mechanical biaxial tensile machine. Four independent axes allow for a maximum load of 150 kN. Figure 3 shows the setup of the tensile machine. Below the specimen a GOM Aramis 4M system is installed to measure the full displacement field via DIC. On the upper side of the specimen five markers are placed for integrated strain measurement (see Figure 2). These points are used for the active midpoint control of the system, which allows for load application without bending in the specimen's arms, even for highly heterogeneous materials.

The experimental procedure is depicted in Figure 4. The average force and strain in the x_1 - and x_2 -

Fig. 3: Biaxial tensile machine (ITM)

direction, in the four load steps (i) to (iv), indicated in 4 (a) and (b), are plotted over time.

First, the specimen is loaded with uniaxial tension in the x_1 -direction (i). The axes in the x_2 -direction maintain a low contact force. Therefore, lateral contraction is observed in the strain path. For every load step, the load is held up for a relaxation time to let most of the viscous strains relax out. In the second load step (ii), uniaxial tension in the x_2 -direction is performed. The same strain of 0.25% in the loading direction requires a lower force, indicating the material anisotropy.

The next load steps are both biaxial: load step (iii) has a loading ratio of 1 : 1, resulting in biaxial tension with equal strains in the loading directions. Load step (iv) shows a loading ratio of 1 : -1, i.e. tension in the x_1 and compression in the x_2 -direction, with the same magnitude as in (iii).

Fig. 4: Experimental procedure

4 INVERSE PARAMETER IDENTIFICATION

4.1 Definition of the inverse Problem

In biaxial tensile experiments, the stress and strain fields in the specimen are heterogeneous. Due to this heterogeneity, the material parameters cannot be identified directly, but may be obtained by the solution of an inverse problem. The direct problem is defined by the strain displacement relation, the impulse balance, the boundary conditions and the following constitutive equations for the strain tensor ε and stress tensor σ

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma &= \mathbb{C}_{\text{trans}}[\varepsilon] + \mathbb{C}_{\text{iso}}[\varepsilon - \varepsilon'_v], \\ \dot{\varepsilon}'_v + \frac{1}{\tau}\varepsilon'_v &= \frac{1}{\tau}\varepsilon', \\ \varepsilon'_v(0) &= \mathbf{0}. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Hereby, a material model with an elastic transversely isotropic stiffness $\mathbb{C}_{\text{trans}}$ in parallel with a Maxwell element with an isotropic stiffness \mathbb{C}_{iso} and relaxation time τ is used. The material is assumed to behave viscous incompressible, therefore the viscous strain ε_v is equal to its deviatoric part. This boundary value problem is solved with the FEM.

Furthermore, if the material parameters are $\underline{p} \in \mathcal{P}$, the numerically calculated strain field is $\varepsilon^{\text{sim}} \in \mathcal{U}^{\text{sim}}$, whereas \mathcal{P} is the space of material parameters and \mathcal{U}^{sim} the solution space of the FEM for strains, the inverse problem can be defined by

$$\text{Find } \underline{p} \in \mathcal{P}, \text{ that resolves } \varepsilon^{\text{sim}}(\underline{p}) = \varepsilon^{\text{exp}}. \quad (2)$$

It should be noted that a perfect equality of the strain fields ε^{exp} and $\varepsilon^{\text{sim}}(\underline{p})$ cannot be reached due to measurement uncertainties or modeling errors [14]. A solution of the inverse problem is, however, obtained by minimizing the correlation function $f(\underline{p})$ that describes the error of the experimental and simulated strains. Vector $\underline{r}(\underline{p})$, that describes the strain deviation $\underline{r}(\underline{p})$ is introduced as well. In $f(\underline{p})$ and $\underline{r}(\underline{p})$ only the measurable in-plane strains are considered

$$\underline{r}(\underline{p}) = \sum_{i=1}^K \sum_{j=1}^N \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon_{11,i,j}^{\text{sim}}(\underline{p}) - \varepsilon_{11,i,j}^{\text{exp}} \\ \varepsilon_{22,i,j}^{\text{sim}}(\underline{p}) - \varepsilon_{22,i,j}^{\text{exp}} \\ \gamma_{12,i,j}^{\text{sim}}(\underline{p}) - \gamma_{12,i,j}^{\text{exp}} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (3)$$

Since the meshes of the experimentally measured strain field is much finer discretized, than the FEM simulation solution, both results are compared on a comparison mesh. A mapping algorithm interpolates

the strain fields on a comparison mesh with the spatial coordinates $\mathbf{x}_i \in \Omega$, $i = 1 \dots K$ and discrete times $t_j \in \mathcal{T}$, $j = 1 \dots N$.

Using the strain vector $\underline{\varepsilon} = (\varepsilon_{11}, \varepsilon_{11}, \gamma_{12})^T$, the error function $f(\underline{p})$ and the strain deviation $\underline{r}(\underline{p})$ the inverse problem can be rewritten as

$$f(\underline{p}) = \|\underline{r}(\underline{p})\|_2^2 = \underline{r}(\underline{p})^T \underline{r}(\underline{p}) \rightarrow \min_{\underline{p} \in \mathcal{P}}. \quad (4)$$

4.2 Identifiable material parameters

For transversely isotropic materials Hooke's law can be written as

$$\begin{pmatrix} \tilde{\varepsilon}_{11} \\ \tilde{\varepsilon}_{22} \\ \tilde{\varepsilon}_{33} \\ \tilde{\gamma}_{12} \\ \tilde{\gamma}_{13} \\ \tilde{\gamma}_{23} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{E_t} & -\frac{\nu_t}{E_t} & -\frac{\nu_t}{E_t} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{\nu_t}{E_t} & \frac{1}{E_p} & -\frac{\nu_p}{E_p} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{\nu_t}{E_t} & -\frac{\nu_p}{E_p} & \frac{1}{E_p} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{G_t} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{G_t} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{2(1+\nu_p)}{E_p} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{\sigma}_{11} \\ \tilde{\sigma}_{22} \\ \tilde{\sigma}_{33} \\ \tilde{\sigma}_{12} \\ \tilde{\sigma}_{13} \\ \tilde{\sigma}_{23} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (5)$$

Hereby, the quantities $\tilde{\varepsilon}_i$ and $\tilde{\sigma}_i$ are the stresses and strains in the homogeneous material coordinate system and E_t , ν_t , ν_p , E_p and G_t are material parameters. The following relations are obtained considering only the measurable in-plane strains

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\varepsilon}_{11} &= \frac{1}{E_t} \tilde{\sigma}_{11} - \frac{\nu_t}{E_t} \tilde{\sigma}_{22} - \frac{\nu_t}{E_t} \tilde{\sigma}_{33}, \\ \tilde{\varepsilon}_{22} &= -\frac{\nu_t}{E_t} \tilde{\sigma}_{11} + \frac{1}{E_p} \tilde{\sigma}_{22} - \frac{\nu_p}{E_p} \tilde{\sigma}_{33}, \\ \tilde{\gamma}_{12} &= \frac{1}{G_t} \tilde{\sigma}_{12}. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Since the stress in the out of plane direction $\tilde{\sigma}_{33}$ on the surface of the plate is zero, ν_p cannot be identified. Including the shear modulus G and the relaxation time τ of the Maxwell element, seven material parameters are identified

$$\underline{p} = (E_t \quad E_p \quad \nu_t \quad G_t \quad \alpha \quad G \quad \tau)^T. \quad (7)$$

The angle α describes the orientation of the local material coordinate system.

4.3 Numerical treatment of the optimization

The optimization problem stated in (4) can be solved by the Gauss-Newton method [12]. The Jacobian is defined as

$$J_{ij}(\underline{p}) = \frac{\partial r_i(\underline{p})}{\partial p_j} = \frac{\partial \varepsilon_i^{\text{sim}}(\underline{p})}{\partial p_j}. \quad (8)$$

The iterative algorithm is given by

$$\underline{p}^{k+1} = \underline{p}^k - \left[\underline{J}(\underline{p}^k)^T \underline{J}(\underline{p}^k) \right]^{-1} \underline{J}(\underline{p}^k)^T \underline{r}(\underline{p}^k). \quad (9)$$

Additionally, a damping factor β^k leads to a more robust convergence behavior

$$\underline{p}^{k+1} = \underline{p}^k - \beta^k \Delta \underline{p}^k. \quad (10)$$

Here, the Jacobian is calculated analytically. This requires a definition of the implicit function \mathbf{K} :

$$\mathbf{K} = \boldsymbol{\sigma} - \mathbb{C}_{\text{trans}}[\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}] - \mathbb{C}_{\text{iso}}[\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}'_v] = \mathbf{0}. \quad (11)$$

The partial differentiation with respect to the scalar material parameters leads to

$$\frac{d\mathbf{K}}{dp_i} = \underbrace{\frac{d\boldsymbol{\sigma}}{dp_i}}_{\mathbf{0}} - \frac{d(\mathbb{C}_{\text{trans}} + \mathbb{C}_{\text{iso}})}{dp_i}[\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}] - (\mathbb{C}_{\text{trans}} + \mathbb{C}_{\text{iso}}) \left[\frac{d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}{dp_i} \right] + \frac{d\mathbb{C}_{\text{iso}}}{dp_i}[\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}'_v] + \mathbb{C}_{\text{iso}} \left[\frac{d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}'_v}{dp_i} \right] = \mathbf{0}, \quad (12)$$

while it is assumed, that the stress is independent of the material parameters, if the tensile boundary conditions are applied as Neumann boundary conditions.

By applying the chain rule to the evolution equation of $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}'_v$ equation (12) leads to expressions that can either be estimated after the simulation or incrementally to obtain the sought for derivative $d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}/dp_i$:

$$\frac{d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}{dp_i} = \left(\mathbb{C}_{\text{trans}} + \frac{\tau}{\tau + \Delta t} \mathbb{C}_{\text{iso}} \right)^{-1} \left(-\frac{d(\mathbb{C}_{\text{trans}} + \mathbb{C}_{\text{iso}})}{dp_i}[\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}] + \frac{d\mathbb{C}_{\text{iso}}}{dp_i}[\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}'_v] + \mathbb{C}_{\text{iso}} \left[\frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}'_v}{\partial p_i} \right] \right). \quad (13)$$

A split optimization procedure, where first the five elastic parameters were identified before the viscous parameters parameter identification, increased the algorithm stability and computational effort significantly. Additionally it was necessary to increase the strain rate to identify the viscoelastic material parameters robustly.

4.4 Identified material parameters

Fig. 5: Selected comparisons of simulated and measured strain and displacement fields, for uniaxial tension in the x_1 -direction. Here the x_1 -direction is aligned horizontally and the x_2 -direction vertically (sample LFT-NV-2).

Figure 5 depicts a comparison between measured and simulated strain and displacement fields. The samples are labeled with the scheme 'LFT-XX-N' whereas 'XX' defines one of two slightly varied geometries ('V' and 'NV') and 'N' indicates the specimen position in the LFT plate (see also Figure 2). Hereby one can observe local heterogeneities, however, the qualitative and quantitative trends show a good agreement. Despite the fitting of the strain fields, the displacement fields (Figures 5 (g) and 5 (h)) in the loading direction show a similar asymmetry which can be explained by a material orientation offset from the x_1 -direction.

Figure 6 shows the evolution of E_t , E_p , and G_t along the flow length. For all of the tested specimen the transversely isotropic direction is close to the flow direction ($\alpha < 7^\circ$). The specimens show an increase of stiffness in the flow direction with an increasing flow length, and a decrease of stiffness perpendicular to the flow direction. This behavior is due to the increasing degree of fiber orientation in moldfilling shear

Fig. 6: Evolution of E_t , E_p , and G_t along the flow length

flow.

Figure 7 compares the biaxial loading step (iii) with the superposition of the two uniaxial loading cases

Fig. 7: Comparison of biaxial loading and superpositioned uniaxial loading cases with the scale factors β_i and β_{ii} . Here the x_1 -direction is aligned horizontally and the x_2 -direction vertically (sample LFT-NV-2).

(i) and (ii). Here, β_i and β_{ii} are scale factors calculated by the ratio of the applied forces in the different loading cases. All strain fields, show a good agreement of the strain fields. The similarity between the local inhomogeneities, clearly visible in Figures 7 (c) and (d) suggest the assumption that, these local inhomogeneities' origins are due to defects in the tested material.

The comparisons of transient displacements for the viscoelastic parameter identification is shown in Figure 8. Here, Δu_i denotes the distance between two points aligned in the x_i direction. As the strains were tried to maintain constant by the video extensometer and control unit in the shown time slots, the forces decreased by 22 – 30%.

Fig. 8: Displacement of measurement marks for experiment and simulation with a viscoelastic material model (sample LFT-NV-2)

5 HOMOGENIZATION OF ELASTIC PROPERTIES USING FIBER ORIENTATION DISTRIBUTION FUNCTIONS

5.1 Modeling preliminaries

The microstructure $\Omega = \Omega_F \cup \Omega_M$ of LFT is assumed to consist of a matrix Ω_M and a set of N fibers $\Omega_F = \{\Omega_\alpha : \alpha = 1, \dots, N\}$. The matrix is characterized by its stiffness tensor \mathbb{C}_M and volume fraction c_M . Accordingly, the fiber with number α is specified by the orientation of the axis \mathbf{n}_α , the length l_α , the radius r_α , the volume fraction c_α , and the stiffness tensor \mathbb{C}_α . The aspect ratio $a_\alpha = l_\alpha / (2r_\alpha)$ denotes the ratio of the length to the diameter of each fiber. The total fiber volume fraction is indicated with $c_F = 1 - c_M = \sum_{\alpha=1}^N c_\alpha$. The material behavior of the fibers is assumed to be uniform, e.g., $\mathbb{C}_\alpha = \mathbb{C}_F$ for $\alpha = 1, \dots, N$. The term *phase* comprises all constituents, which have the same stiffness, geometry, and orientation.

5.2 Estimation of the fiber orientation distribution function

The estimation of the fiber orientation distribution function (FODF) is based on the incomplete information of the fiber orientation tensors using the maximum entropy method [2]. This method can be stated in the irreducible part of the second and fourth-order fiber orientation tensors, denoted as \mathbf{A}' and \mathbb{A}' [10], as

$$S := - \int_S \bar{f}(\mathbf{n}) \ln(\bar{f}(\mathbf{n})) \, dS \rightarrow \max, \quad (14)$$

$$G := \int_S \bar{f}(\mathbf{n}) \, dS - 1 \stackrel{!}{=} 0, \quad (15)$$

$$\mathbf{G} := \int_S \bar{f}(\mathbf{n}) (\mathbf{n} \otimes \mathbf{n})' \, dS - \mathbf{A}' \stackrel{!}{=} \mathbf{0}, \quad (16)$$

$$\mathbb{G} := \int_S \bar{f}(\mathbf{n}) (\mathbf{n} \otimes \mathbf{n} \otimes \mathbf{n} \otimes \mathbf{n})' \, dS - \mathbb{A}' \stackrel{!}{=} \mathbf{0}, \quad (17)$$

with S being the information-theoretic entropy [19, 8, 9], and \mathbf{G} and \mathbb{G} defining the moment equations. This is a quantitative measure of the quality of the estimate. Equation (15) is the constraint that the FODF is normalized whereas the following equations (16) and (17) guarantee the reproduction of the known information. The arising nonlinear constrained optimization problem is solved numerically with the Lagrange multiplier method:

$$\mathcal{L} = S - LG - \mathbf{L} \cdot \mathbf{G} - \mathbb{L} \cdot \mathbb{G}. \quad (18)$$

Here L , \mathbf{L} and \mathbb{L} denote the Lagrange multiplier of first, second and fourth order.

5.3 Interaction direct derivative estimate

The interaction direct derivative (IDD) estimate, proposed by Zheng and Du [20] is based on the effective self-consistent scheme [5], which for its part is based on the three-phase model. Here, the inclusions

are embedded in a matrix material region, directly. This inclusion-matrix cell itself is embedded in the unknown effective medium. The advantage of the IDD lies in its explicit structure, which is valid for multi-phase composites with different material symmetries and distributions.

The following prescription gives the IDD estimate of the properties of the effective medium for an ∞ -phase composite, where the inclusion phases amount to a total volume fraction of c_F , and differ only in their orientation:

$$\mathbb{C}^{\text{IDD}} = \mathbb{C}_M + \left(\mathbb{I}^s - c_F \int_S f(\mathbf{n}) \mathbb{N}(\mathbf{n}) \mathbb{P}^D(\mathbf{n}) dS \right)^{-1} \left(c_F \int_S f(\mathbf{n}) \mathbb{N}(\mathbf{n}) dS \right), \quad (19)$$

with $\mathbb{N}(\mathbf{n}) = (\mathbb{C}(\mathbf{n}) - \mathbb{C}_M) (\mathbb{I}^s + \mathbb{P}(\mathbf{n}) (\mathbb{C}(\mathbf{n}) - \mathbb{C}_M))^{-1}$. Here, $\mathbb{P} = \mathbb{P}(\mathbb{C}_M, \mathbf{Z}(\mathbf{n}))$ is Hill's polarization tensor:

$$\mathbb{P}(\mathbb{C}_M, \mathbf{Z}(\tilde{\mathbf{n}})) = \frac{1}{4\pi \det(\mathbf{Z})} \int_S \mathbb{H}(\mathbf{n}) (\mathbf{n} \cdot (\mathbf{Z}^{-T} \mathbf{Z}^{-1} \mathbf{n}))^{-3/2} dS, \quad (20)$$

with $\mathbb{H}(\mathbf{n}) = \mathbb{I}^s (\mathbf{K}^{-1} \square (\mathbf{n} \otimes \mathbf{n})) \mathbb{I}^s$, $\mathbf{K} = \mathbb{C}_M \llbracket \mathbf{n} \otimes \mathbf{n} \rrbracket$. The polarization tensor depends on the matrix stiffness \mathbb{C}_M and the description of the ellipsoidal geometry $\mathbf{Z}(\mathbf{n}) = \mathbf{Q}^T \mathbf{Z}_0 \mathbf{Q}$ with a homogeneous aspect ratio. Whereby $\mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{n})$ is an orthogonal tensor, which rotates the reference geometry \mathbf{Z}_0 in the direction \mathbf{n} . \mathbf{Z}_0 the description of a reference ellipsoid:

$$\|\mathbf{Z}_0 \mathbf{x}\|^2 = \mathbf{x} \cdot (\mathbf{Z}_0^T \mathbf{Z}_0 \mathbf{x}) \leq 1. \quad (21)$$

\mathbf{x} specifies a position vector in the three-dimensional space. The inverse eigenvalues of \mathbf{Z}_0 correspond to the half axis of the ellipsoid with a specific orientation \mathbf{n}_0 . In equation (21), $\det(\mathbf{Z})$ is the determinant of \mathbf{Z} .

If the matrix-inclusion cell takes on an ellipsoidal shape, then $\mathbb{P}^D = \mathbb{P}(\mathbb{C}_M, \mathbf{Z}^D(\mathbf{n}))$ is the polarization tensor corresponding to an ellipsoidal inclusion with geometry of the matrix-inclusion cell $\mathbf{Z}^D(\mathbf{n})$, which is embedded in an infinite matrix with the stiffness \mathbb{C}_M . The shape of the matrix-inclusion cell defines the inclusion distribution in the composite. In the present work, $\mathbf{Z}^D(\mathbf{n}) = \mathbf{Z}(\mathbf{n})$ is assumed.

6 COMPARISON OF THE EXPERIMENTAL AND HOMOGENIZED PROPERTIES

In the following the elastic properties homogenized in Section 5 are compared to the results of the inverse parameter identification in Section 4.

Figure 9 compares the strain fields obtained by DIC, fitted simulation and homogenized properties with the IDD estimate for loading case (iii). In the last column the magnitude of the deviation of the strain fields obtained by simulation and DIC is shown. The strain ε_{11} shows a good agreement in all three fields. Horizontally in the middle of the upper third, there is a spot that seems to be much softer than the other points. This can be observed in Figures 9 (h), (l), Figure 5 and Figure 7.

The magnitude of ε_{22} is significantly underestimated by the homogenization. This could either be due to an overestimation of the Young's modulus in x_2 direction or underestimation of lateral contraction in this direction. In general the shear field seems to be predicted with a good precision, however the measured shear strain shows comparably high fluctuations.

Homogenization with the well established Mori-Tanaka (MT) [15] scheme lead to, except for negligible differences, the same fields than the IDD scheme, and therefore is not shown here.

The Young's modulus is defined as the ratio of stress and strain in tensile direction \mathbf{d} , and therefore can be expressed as [3]

$$\frac{1}{E(\mathbf{d})} = \mathbf{d} \otimes \mathbf{d} \cdot \mathbb{S}[\mathbf{d} \otimes \mathbf{d}]. \quad (22)$$

The Young's modulus plots of the in-plane (x_1 - x_2) direction are show in Figure 10 for all three specimen locations. Here, the compliance tensor of the experimental results was rotated from the local transversely isotropic material orientation in the global coordinate system. The evolution of the anisotropy ratio is

Fig. 9: Selected comparisons of simulated and measured strain fields, for tension in the x_1 -direction (aligned horizontally) and compression in the x_2 -direction (aligned vertically) (sample LFT-NV-2)

similar to the one shown in Figure 6. However it is observed, that for both tested specimen series ('N' and 'NV') and all positions, the Young's modulus in x_2 -direction are below the ones estimated with MT or IDD schemes. However, the stiffness in the flow direction is estimated quite well. The elastic properties homogenized by IDD and MT coincide almost perfectly.

7 CONCLUSIONS

The inverse identification of viscoelastic material parameters with an anisotropic elastic behavior was introduced for biaxial tensile tests of LFT. The introduction of a correlation function comparing the measured and calculated FEM fields allowed for a straight forward estimation of the gradient for the Gauss-Newton procedure. In order to achieve robust convergence, a two-step parameter identification was used, which first identified the elastic and in a second step the viscous material parameters.

It was irrelevant for the elastic material parameters, if both uniaxial loading steps ((i) and (ii)) were considered, one biaxial loading step ((iii) or (iv)), or any combination of the four. The material fits well to the simulated material model, however shows spots of high deviations of the strain fields. These deviations suggest material homogeneities, i.e. air inclusions, variations in fiber volume fractions or nonimpregnated fiber bundles.

The material shows a, for LFT typical, evolution of moduli along the flow length, whereas the anisotropy ratio significantly increases from position one to position two, and is similar in position two and three. For a more statistically reliable characterization of material parameters more than the two samples per position need to be considered.

The FODF was obtained by additional information of the maximum entropy method, whereby the effective elastic behavior was estimated with the IDD scheme.

The homogenized properties showed a good agreement with the tensile tests. But, some components of \mathbb{S} , especially the stiffness perpendicular to the flow direction require further investigation.

Fig. 10: Directional dependent Young's modulus

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The research documented in this manuscript was initiated by the German-Canadian research group "Integrated engineering of continuous-discontinuous long fiber reinforced polymer structures". The support of the group by the German Research Foundation (DFG) is gratefully acknowledged.

I would like to thank the Chair of Lightweight Technology of the KIT Institute of Vehicle System Technology (FAST) and the KIT Institute for Applied Materials - Materials Science and Engineering (IAM-WK) for providing the μ CT data, as well as the Fraunhofer Institute for Chemical Technology for providing the tested LFT plates.

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